

Tourism and Economic Development A Case Study InTamil Nadu

Dr. T. Musthafa

*Assistant Professor, Department of Economics
Sadakathullah Appa College, Tirunelveli*

Abstract

Tourism industry offers much scope for earning foreign exchange and it stimulates the rate of growth of the economy. Through interaction of natural, human and cultural factors, it functions as a major means of recreation. Modern tourism results from the recognition of a fundamental right of the human being to rest and leisure. This study analyses the duration of stay and level of expenditure by the sample respondents and the economic impact of tourism in the study area. As the analysis has shown that the tourism industry does not create any negative impact in the study area the Government should come forward to develop leisure tourism, beach tourism, religious tourism, rural tourism and medical tourism especially in the backward regions, which will directly help reduce the regional inequalities

Keywords: *Tourism, Impact, Economy, Development*

Introduction

Tourism is the movement of people to places away from their usual place of residence and work with a motive to relax their mind and refresh their body. In modern times, tourism is considered as one of the important industries, which contributes to the socio-economic development of a country. It also refers to the phenomenon and relationship arising out of travel and stay of nonresidents. Tourism industry offers much scope for earning foreign exchange and it stimulates the rate of growth of the economy. Through interaction of natural, human and cultural factors, it functions as a major means of recreation. Modern tourism results from the recognition of a fundamental right of the human being to rest and leisure. It has become a factor contributing to individual betterment and mutual understanding among individuals and people. It has acquired cultural and moral dimensions, which must be fostered and protected against the harmful distortions. Tourism is made up of several industries, which offer myriad types of goods and services demanded by consumer-tourists. It is due to its size and scope, marked as one of the largest trades in the world. Despite its magnitude, tourism promotion, operation and foundation were not clearly understood by both public and private agencies. Tamil Nadu is absolutely unique as a tourism destination. Tamil Nadu flanked by a coastline on the east and the ghats in the west, has topographical beauty, richness of resources, architectural, cultural and artistic glory. Besides there are numerous tourist spots like wild life parks, pilgrim centres etc. Foreign and domestic tourists' arrival in Tamil Nadu during 2016 was 34.85 crores, which included 34.38 crores domestic tourists and 47.20 lakhs of foreign tourists. The annual growth rate of the same has been quite considerable in the last 16 years, particularly upto 2014, while in the last two years, the annual growth rate has declined in both categories.

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Objectives of the Study

1. To analyse the duration of stay and level of expenditure by the sample respondents and
2. To trace the economic impact of tourism in the study area.

Hypotheses of the Study

1. There is no significant relationship between income of the tourists and growth of tourism and
2. Growth of tourism does not significantly create any positive impact on the economy.

Significance of the Study

This study assumes greater significance owing to the fact that tourism promotes and also attempts to establish tourism as a major industry to the development of cities and towns. The demand for tourism is elastic and hence, socio economic growth in other countries will enhance the demand for tourism in India. Many developed countries including Singapore spend much to promote tourism. The policy makers must remove the irritants in India's tourism development and formulate such policies which will promote tourism and in turn will help improve socio-economic development of the country. All these suggest that the present study is a more significant one.

Review of Literature

Tourism may accelerate changes which are already underway in a community, but it does not by itself introduce changes. Tourism is contributing to changes in value systems, individual behaviour, family relationship, moral conduct, creative expressions, traditional ceremonies and community organizations. Tourism is surely good for the country provided its effects are not harmful to the host population. India has not yet reached a stage where the harmful effects of tourism need to be deliberated upon (Kumar, 1992). Hurray (1970) undertook a case study of Caribbean and analysed the growth and structure of Caribbean tourism and the role of government in the growth of Caribbean tourism and also analysed tourist multipliers and social costs and benefits in the Caribbean. Jenningham (1972) indicates that tourism was born in

the seventeenth century and English were the first to practice. Young and Turner (1973) give prominence in the seminal works based on the psychological, social and cultural effects of tourism. Pueblo (1973-1989) made field study and collected data for tourism management in New Mexico. Doxey (1976) examined the resentments, which may result from tourist-host interactions. Bevy (1977) presented a general overview of tourist development. Wall and Wright examined the environmental impact studies on tourism. Coltman's (1981) contribution to the literature on tourism industry is highly praise worthy in the sense that it is considered one of the best contributions on tourism marketing. His work serves as a guide for tourism promoters, such as Governments, destination area, transports, channel of distribution - intermediaries - tourist agents, tour operators, suppliers such as hotels / lodges restaurants, are interrelated with each other to create successful tourism marketing. Foster (1986) has found that tourism has been recognized as a source of employment. It is highly labour intensive industry offering employment to both semi - skilled and the unskilled. Being a service industry it creates employment opportunities for the local population. Besides, economic benefits to a country by way of foreign exchange earnings and employment generation. Tourism also makes a tremendous contribution to the improvement of social and political understanding (Bhatia, 1989). Tourism is a painless procedure of transfer of real resource from industrially capital surplus developed countries to low income developing countries. It is a very important source for maximizing foreign exchange earnings for not only developed countries of the world, but also the developing countries. Tourism is also being recognized as a source of employment. It is a highly labour intensive industry offering employment to both the semiskilled and unskilled (Kaul, 1994).

Methodology of the Study

The type of survey usually adopted was the survey of the resident population of a tourist spots. Questions were posed to them on their perception of impact of tourism on them. Thirdly, the survey of visitors in the tourist spot is a quite popular method

in case of foreign tourists. Under this method, data were collected either on the spot or at the time of their departure. Fourthly, a survey on establishment is conducted where the employees and the employers of such establishments are covered. The reliability of data provided by these establishments is limited because of the fact that employer always want to guard it as secret. Primary data of the study have been collected from the sample tourists, hotel and shop owners, STD booth owners other service people such as transport operators, restaurant owners, guest house owners, auto drivers, temple officials of the area. Data collected from tourists include their income, expenditure in the places of visit, nature of commodities and services they bought, number of days of their stay, factors which attracted them to this area and factors which they consider as hurdles or irritants for their pleasant stay. Data on the amount of investment, number of people employed growth of business over the years, nature of commodities sold/ services rendered and their opinion on the growth of tourists, arrival have been collected from shop owners, STD booth owners, guest houses, hotels and restaurant owners, transport operators, temple officials, auto driver using a structured questionnaire, opinions of the residents on the impact of tourism on local area development have also been collected. Secondary data on the quantum of tourist's flow, Government expenditure and other measures to promote tourism have been collected from the Department of Tourism.

Sample Design

Tourists have been selected on the basis of Scientific Sampling Method. The tourists who have travelled either through Indian Tourism Department Travel Bus or Tamil Nadu Tourism Department Travel Bus during the period from April to May 2017 alone constitute the universe. Sample has been drawn from those tourists. There are fluctuations in the number of tourists visiting the place either on the basis of days or seasons. Sixty foreign and domestic tourists have been selected each from Chennai and Mahabalipuram, of which twenty are leisure tourists, thirty are religious tourists, five are beach tourists and five are medical tourists. Fifty shop owners, forty transport operators, and twenty four guest

house owners, sixteen auto drivers, ten STD booth owners twenty restaurant owners, twenty hotels owners, and ten temple officials each from Chennai and Mahabalipuram have been chosen as samples. Hence, in all 310 sample respondents have been chosen, comprising 120 tourists, 180 residents and ten temple officials, with proportionate weight to both Chennai and Mahabalipuram. Well-structured questionnaires have been used to collect data from all the respondents. Separate questionnaires have been used to account the investment growth over the year and their opinions about the problems in promoting tourism have also been collected.

Analysis of Data and Discussion

The basic aim of the present study is to analyse various kinds of impact of tourism in Chennai and Mahabalipuram. The impact of tourism can be assessed from those people who are depending on this sector for their livelihood or whose major part of income is generated from this sector, apart from the tourists themselves. Thus, the sample respondents are categorised into tourists, residents and temple officials in the two locations. Residents include transport operators, guest house owners, telephone booth owners, shopkeepers, hoteliers, restaurant owners and auto drivers.

Length of Stay of the Tourists

The total sample size of 310 respondents also includes 120 tourists, 60 each from Chennai and Mahabalipuram. To understand the social and economic impacts of the tourists, various information regarding their length of stay during a visit, number of time they visited Chennai, and the amount of their spending on tour as a percentage of their annual income have been gathered. The total number of tourists is classified into local tourists, tourists from other states and foreign tourists depending on their place of origin. In this section, the economic aspects of the tourists are analysed.

Summary Statistics

The analysis in the previous sections has been done on the basis of frequency and ratio distribution pertaining to various aspects of the sample respondents. Ratio analysis which is done using the class intervals

will not provide accurate data regarding the variables like monthly income level of the respondents, their total household income, age level and also the proportion of money spent on tour. Descriptive statistics which include mean, minimum, maximum and also standard deviation are capable of providing some more detail on such variables. In this section, the analysis is done by using the descriptive statistics on some of the variables pertaining to different categories of respondents. To begin with, the descriptive statistics regarding the age, income levels as well as the percentage of amount spent on tour are provided for the two locations separately.

Conclusion

As the analysis has shown that the tourism industry does not create any negative impact in the study area the Government should come forward to develop leisure tourism, beach tourism, religious tourism, rural tourism and medical tourism especially in the backward regions, which will directly help reduce the regional inequalities. Moreover, there are many tourists attractions in India and also in Tamil Nadu and as the tourism industry is projected to

grow at a rapid rate, the Union Government and the State Government need to be proactive in attracting foreign tourists which will also increase foreign exchange earnings

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